

The Moral Dimension of Critical Thinking

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Research Article

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Abstract: Critical thinking has an important role in the advancement of personal development. Undoubtedly, thanks to critical thinking, individuals can use their abilities better and become active in society. This system of thinking can have positive results on students, especially in the development of cognitive and creative thinking in education. Critical thinking, education as well as philosophy, literature, cinema, history, geography, biology, health, etc. has a relationship with disciplines. Critical thinking plays an important role in understanding disciplines and learning basic concepts. The most basic purpose of critical thinking is to stick to moral attitudes. When criticizing in a discussion environment, it is important to stick to moral principles rather than the subject of the problem being discussed. In this context, the conceptual framework of critical thinking will be discussed. Critical thinking; its relationship with philosophy, education, literature, art, and other sciences will be examined. Finally, the moral dimension of critical thinking and the principles to be followed will be mentioned while criticizing will be mentioned.

Keywords: Thought, critical thinking, ethics, moral dimension, moral principles.

1. The Conceptual Framework of Critical Thinking

Thinking: using mental abilities so that you can form ideas and come to conclusions; have a conscious mind to reason, remember experiences, make decisions; It is to use the mind rationally and objectively when evaluating or dealing with a given situation.¹ In this context, people can think while making judgments and based on human behavior. Other functions of thought include logical reasoning, making connections between events and facts, and obtaining conclusions from premises. Let's look at the concept of criticism, which means distinguishing, evaluating and judging, which we can count as ways of thinking.

“Criticism is the work of examining a person, a work, a subject to find and show their right and wrong sides.”² In general, although the word criticism has a negative connotation in the human mind, it should be known that this term does not actually mean negativity. “Learning to think critically is learning to look deep into things and be able to look well, properly, in a clear way, adequately and logically.”³ In this context, the fact that criticism gains meaning and is open to the ideas put forward makes the solution of problems even easier. For critical thinking, “clear thinking, aimed at the well-founded judgment, is using appropriate standards of evaluation to attempt to determine the true worth, virtue, or worth of something.”⁴

The conceptual framework of critical thinking has a wide range of meanings. There are many ways to explain critical thinking. Some of those:

1. The art of analyzing and evaluating thought for improvement.

¹ Richard Paul & Elder Linda, *Kritik Düşünce*, çev. Esra Aslan ve Gamze Sart (Ankara: Nobel Yayıncılık, 2016), 447.

² Şükrü Haluk Akalın, *Türkçe Sözlük* (Ankara: Türk Dil Kurumu Yayınları, 2017), 786.

³ Gerd M. Nosich, *Eleştirel Düşünce ve Disiplinler Arası Eleştirel Düşünme Rehberi*, çev. Birsal Aybek (Ankara: Anı Yayıncılık, 2016), 14.

⁴ Paul & Linda, *Kritik Düşünce*, 27.

2. Disciplined self-directed thinking meets appropriate mental standards within a specific shape and field of thinking.

3. Thought commonly indicates mental ability, ability, and behavior.

4. Thinking about your thinking while thinking to make your thinking better: clearer, more precise, more reasonable, and so on.

5. Defined as self-directed self-disciplined thinking towards reasoning at the highest quality level in an unbiased manner.⁵

Three main levels give rise to our need for critical thinking. These are the level of practical decision-making, relevance, and concepts.

At the level of practical decision-making, it is the ability to facilitate daily work and solve problems. How to study more efficiently? Or, choosing clothes for us in a store where there are many kinds of dresses can be given as an example. At the level of significance, it is trying to reconcile the role of critical thinking with the topics we see in the lessons while making a new friend or trying to find a new job. Developing rational attitudes to ourselves and others that make life meaningful. Finally, the effect of critical thinking at the conceptual level is that we can know all the concepts about what it means to be a teacher, student, woman, man, religious, atheist, scientist, artist, an expert in any field we take lessons. We have concepts of what it means to be brave, to be treated fairly, to be smart. We can arrive at a deeper level of critical thinking by critically examining our concepts, becoming more aware that individual concepts help or harm us, and limiting and liberating us.⁶

Critical thinking can be accepted as the most important element of individual and social development. If a misunderstood idea persists in society, it may be because critical thinking is not widespread enough in that society. A person or society with a critical thinking identity shows continuous improvement. We know

⁵ Paul & Linda, *Kritik Düşünce*, 450.

⁶ Nosich, *Eleştirel Düşünce ve Disiplinler Arası Eleştirel Düşünme Rehberi*, 27-28.

that one of the most basic aims of educational institutions that build the individual and society is to gain critical thinking skills and to become widespread. With a critical way of thinking, learning becomes very easy, and the foundations of a student-centered education are laid. Critical thinking plays a very important role in helping students think more fluently and in gaining cognitive skills in education. Students who can produce solutions to social problems with critical thinking are trained.

Questioning is one of the activities carried out to improve students' language, mental and social skills. With questioning, processes such as thinking, understanding, learning, and evaluation are carried out more easily. It is seen that the questioning, which has a long history since the time of Socrates, has come to the fore again with new educational approaches.⁷

According to a study conducted in our country in recent years, the success achieved in a classroom where critical thinking is practiced is as follows:

The positive aspects of the program in line with the findings; Being student-centered, an effort to save education from rote learning, willing participation of students in lessons, increase in students' self-confidence, compliance with teaching principles, relationship with daily life, prompting students for research and examination, suitability for active learning, directing students to love mathematics, taking individual differences into account, content- activity consistency, forcing the teacher to improve, and involving the parents in the process.⁸

Teachers have a great role in helping students gain critical thinking. "Teachers' implementation of activities to develop critical thinking skills in their classrooms will positively affect student achievement and attitude towards the lesson, as it will take into account the individual differences of students. Therefore, first of

⁷ Firdevs Güneş, "Eğitimde Sorgulama Gücü," *Bartın Üniversitesi Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi* 12 (2016), 188-204.

⁸ Erdoğan Köse, "2005 İlk Öğretim Matematik Programının Eğitsel Eleştirel Modeline Göre Değerlendirilmesi," *Adnan Menderes Üniversitesi Eğitim Fakültesi Eğitim Bilimler Dergisi* 2, no. 2 (2011), 1-11.

all, teachers' critical thinking skills should be developed, and it should be ensured that they attach importance to the development of critical thinking in their classrooms. For this purpose, critical thinking should be handled theoretically and practically in both pre-service teacher training programs and in-service training, and it should be an example of how it can be developed through activities."⁹ In this context, critical thinking is not only limited to education but also philosophy, literature, cinema, art, etc. It should be known that it contributes to disciplines such as.

2. The Relationship of Critical Thinking with Other Disciplines

Critical thinking is not specific to only one field but can operate in many fields. This way of thinking can lead to a stronger bond between sciences and the emergence of more original studies.

Critical thinking; is an original tool that is effective in the production of scientific knowledge, the development and advancement of science. critical thinking; tries to look at the sciences from a broad perspective without drawing borders, from a more comprehensive, deep, and broad perspective. Critical thinking demonstrates a positive, intellectual attitude toward the advancement of the sciences. Critical thinking has an active role before and after science. Because creative intelligence, imagination, and prudent critical thinking have been effective in producing scientific knowledge and putting it at the service of mankind.¹⁰

It has been very difficult to give a precise definition to philosophy since history. "Indeed, many people define philosophy as a critical and free-thinking activity or a coherent direction of thought; he says it is an art of thinking arising from questioning and bewilderment. It is possible to see the principles of critical

⁹ Gürcü Koç Erdamar & Gülgün Bangir Alpan, "Eleştirel Düşünme Algısı: Lise Öğretmenleri Üzerine Bir Araştırma," *Elektronik Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi* 62 (2017), 796-797.

¹⁰ Rıdvan Küçükali & Hasibe Akbaş, "Eleştirel Düşüncenin Bilimlerin Gelişmesine Katkıları," *Atatürk Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Dergisi* 19, no. 3 (2015), 1-10.

thinking within the definition of philosophy itself.”¹¹ In this context, “philosophical thought is a thought based on a critical attitude. It is the task of philosophy to try to clarify unquestioned assumptions or assumptions by passing them through the filter of criticism. Criticism, on the other hand, is that consciousness puts a distance between its 'subject' and 'itself', looking at its subject from the opposite side and making evaluations in this direction. Therefore, philosophical thought passes all kinds of material that it receives as data through the mind's critique filter. Since it is a result of an inquiry and research based on reason, contradictory judgments and inconsistent opinions are not included in the evaluations of subjects and concepts in philosophy. For this reason, philosophical thought is the product of a mind that tries to grasp the field of existence, knowledge and values together by acting with the motives of curiosity, doubt, surprise (amazement) and not content with what is presented to it.”¹²

The material used by the people working in other professions and the material used by the philosophers are different. For example, a Computer Engineer is the parts of the computer, which are the keyboard, case, monitor, and network parts, or the material in the hands of a scientist is a microscope. The material used by philosophers is critical thinking skills. This idea workers, who preferred the abstract instead of the concrete material, also paved the way for the development of other sciences.

Philosophical thought is critical thinking; that is, it passes through the mind's critique filter of all kinds of material that it treats as data. This material may be a) provided to her directly by the field of existence to which she is directed, or b) more often than this, it may be material provided by other intellectual activities concerning these fields of existence.¹³

As a result, the existence of the following principles between

¹¹ Ahmet Cevizci, *Felsefeye Giriş* (Ankara: Nobel Yayın Dağıtım, 2010), 7.

¹² Emel Koç, “Felsefe Nedir?,” *Kafkas Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Dergisi* 3 (2009), 221-231.

¹³ Ahmet Arslan, *Felsefeye Giriş* (Ankara: Adres Yayınları, 2013), 32.

philosophy and critical thinking shows the closeness of both fields. These principles are:

- Philosophical thinking is critical/inquiring thinking.

- The rules and methods of philosophical studies, and the theoretical concerns of philosophy (clearness, systematicity, etc.) are parallel to the principles of critical thinking; in other saying; Structural features of philosophical thought point to critical thinking dispositions and skills.

- Philosophy requires critical thinking and critical thinking is a philosophical activity, Philosophical attitude and tendency towards critical thinking are coordinated.

- The fact that individuals who are qualified as wise and critical thinkers have the same characteristics indicates a strong relationship between philosophy and critical thinking.¹⁴

Based on these principles, it can be said that there is a close relationship between philosophy and critical thinking. The discipline with which critical thinking has a close relationship after philosophy is undoubtedly literature.

Literary criticism can be defined as the analysis and interpretation activity carried out within the framework of certain principles in understanding the nature of the literary work and revealing its aesthetic value.¹⁵

The criticisms made here illuminate the background of the works in question. Thanks to criticism, the information and evaluation process reveals the nature of the works. Criticism not only enriches the mind of the reader but also enriches the work in question. This way of thinking creates an atmosphere of controversy and paves the way for cultural enrichment. This increases the number of readers. Thanks to criticism, writers can produce more satisfying works by being more attentive while writing their works. Perhaps the first and most popular task of literary criticism

¹⁴ Senar Alkın Şahin & Nihal Tunca, "Felsefe ve Eleştirel Düşünme," *Trakya Üniversitesi Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi* 5, no. 2 (2015), 203.

¹⁵ Ulaş Bingöl, "Akademik Eleştiri Hakkında Bazı Dikkatler," *Edebi Eleştiri Dergisi* 1, no. 1 (2017), 2-4.

is to introduce works and their creators to the broad public.¹⁶ Your critical thinking is not limited to this area but also shows its effect on art.

Critical thinking has a great contribution in making artistic values meaningful, encouraging fine works and correcting imperfections. “What will happen to art in the absence of criticism, how and in what ways it will continue to exist, whether it can produce alternatives, whether it can protect its own space is the question.”¹⁷ For works made in the name of art to be accepted by society, the artist must be open to criticism. After art, another field in which critical thinking contributes is cinema.

Cinema criticism is a type of writing that deals with the evaluation of a film in terms of art, aesthetics, technique, ideology and sociology. Cinema criticism provides communication between the receiver and the giver, that is, between the creator of the film and the audience, it introduces and evaluates the film.¹⁸

The development and promotion of the art of cinema depends on the widespread use of film criticism. Evaluations and comments can be made on the materials used during the movie criticism, the decor, and the actor roles. When the film reviews are successful, the message that the film wants to give to society can be understood more clearly.

To summarize, critical thinking has influenced many fields due to its multifaceted nature. The above-mentioned critical thinking: It is mentioned how it contributes to the fields of philosophy, education, literature, art, and cinema. Also, “critical thinking in biology is logical reflective biological thinking and is focused on the broad relationship between biology and the world in deciding what to do or believe in biology. To think critically in geography is to reflect on a problem of the space of the earth geographically. In

¹⁶ Yılmaz Özbek, “Eleştiri Üzerine,” *Dergi Park Dergisi* 30 (2017), 1-7.

¹⁷ Güler Bek, “Eleştiri Yokluğunda Sanat,” *Süleyman Demirel Üniversitesi Güzel Sanatlar Fakültesi Hakemli Dergisi* 10 (2012), 1.

¹⁸ Nalan Büker, “Eleştirinin Amacı, Yöntemleri ve Eleştiri Sistemleri,” *Kurgu Dergisi* 9 (1991), 267-268.

nursing, on the other hand, critical thinking emerges as the way an observant, knowledgeable and logical nurse thinks.”¹⁹

3. The Moral Dimension of Critical Thinking

Compare thinking critically with driving a car. There are rules for good driving. (For example, using the lanes when entering a highway), but simply following the rules does not make you a good driver. To be a good driver, you must follow the rules logically. What does it mean? For example, a driver's awareness that the purpose of lanes is to keep traffic flowing smoothly and to reduce congestion for slow and fast cars also affects how he or she will use lanes, depending on weather and traffic conditions. Note that this is an open-ended list of things a sensible driver is aware of when changing lanes.²⁰ Undoubtedly, a wrong move by the driver will cause an accident in the traffic, and worse still, the lives of the people in the traffic will come to an end. So, if the driver of a car acts as if there is no car on the road but himself, there will be a traffic accident. If a person says what she wants in the direction she knows without thinking about how it affects the other person while talking, communication accidents will occur, just like in traffic. Some people were injured and died as a result of these accidents with human relations. Those who are offended, separated, and offended constitute the wounded, those who shut themselves in and are buried in solitude, those who die.²¹

There are two types of criticism in interpersonal communication. It is constructive and destructive. Constructive attitude A problem that arises between two people is discussed and discussed. As a result of this discussion, healthy communication is established between the two people. The destructive attitude is used to discuss a problem that has been learned and emerged since childhood. In this destructive attitude, the two people distance themselves from each other as a result of the argument, and

¹⁹ Nosich, *Eleştirel Düşünce ve Disiplinler Arası Eleştirel Düşünme Rehberi*, 91-96.

²⁰ Nosich, *Eleştirel Düşünce ve Disiplinler Arası Eleştirel Düşünme Rehberi*, 5.

²¹ Doğan Cüceloğlu, *Yeniden İnsan İnsana* (İstanbul: Remzi Kitabevi, 2022), 17.

their relationship weakens and breaks.²² Therefore, morality has a role in establishing healthy communication between people, revealing their personalities, and taking actions and attitudes.

There are multiple verses of the Quran related to the subject. The Qur'an first orders people to stay away from rhetoric that insults each other's values. "Woe to all those who pull behind their backs and make fun of their eyebrows."²³ Secondly, he warns in the Qur'an that anyone who criticizes should check the source of information: "O you who believe! If a sinner brings you news, seek its origin. Otherwise, you will unknowingly taunt a people and regret what you have done."²⁴ In another verse, people are warned with the verse "do not follow what you do not know about".²⁵ Another moral attitude that the Qur'an draws attention to is that a person uses soft language and smiling. In the verse: "As a mercy from Allah, you were gentle with them. If you had been rude, hard-hearted, they would have dispersed from your surroundings."²⁶ Another similar message in this verse is that we see that Prophet Moses and Harun used this method when they invited Pharaoh to Islam. Allah commands both prophets: "Go to Pharaoh, you two. Probably it was few. Then speak softly to him. Thus, he contemplates (understands) or feels awe."²⁷

A group of people needs to exchange ideas to gain information or to make a topic a topic of discussion. The condition for this group to overcome the difficulties encountered during the assembly is the moral attitudes it will display. For example, it is not good behavior to stick to one's own opinion during a discussion. It is an immoral attitude to ignore the other person and to look at his/her views with prejudice. Everyone has to seek the truth and reveal the truth. The unjust person should not be proud or arrogant and turn away from the right side. As a matter of fact, it was revealed

²² Cüceloğlu, *Yeniden İnsan İnsana*, 198.

²³ Surah al-Humaza, 1.

²⁴ Surah al-Hujurat, 46.

²⁵ Surah al-Isra', 36.

²⁶ Surah Al Imran, 159.

²⁷ Surah Taha, 43-44.

to the Prophet, “Then either we or you are on the right path or in a clear error”,²⁸ while he was arguing with the polytheists. In this verse, the Prophet is ordered to avoid showing bigotry. The message has been given that whatever the right is, it should be on its side. Here we are faced with an extremely moderate and tolerant example that complies with the rules of discussion. The Messenger of Allah first said to the polytheists, “One of us is definitely on the right path and the other is on the wrong path.” But then it doesn't specify who is right. In this way, he wants to draw the interlocutor to think and evaluate the issue. The Prophet is a guide and teacher. His sole purpose is to guide the polytheists to the right path. It's not about silencing them with argument and humiliating them.”²⁹ In this context, this method of discussion of the Prophet should set an example for other educators.

In that case, people should use appropriate language while criticizing and should aim to make correct statements. One should avoid being self-centered in the context of arguments, believing that “I am always right”. One should not get caught up in the ego of inanity and enlarge it, otherwise, it is very difficult for one to reach the truth. If the purpose is to nurture the “me” and to prioritize the “me” during critical thinking, if the criticism of the other party is not taken as a rule, then there is no situation in which he will benefit from the environment. This does not benefit the person but does harm. You must know how to listen as well as speak. You have to take the risk of being criticized as much as you can criticize.”³⁰ So, what are the moral principles to be followed in criticism? Let's stay on this topic.

4. Moral Principles to be Followed in Criticism

For an individual or a society to be built, it is necessary to live in accordance with moral values. An environment where moral values are disregarded leaves its place in chaos. One of the biggest

²⁸ Surah Saba', 24.

²⁹ Murat Kayacan, *Kuranın Hz. Peygamberi Eğitmesi* (İstanbul: Ekin Yayınları, 2007), 48.

³⁰ Abdullatif Acar, “Eleştiri Ahlakı,” *Burhan İlim Kültür Dergisi* 146 (2017).

problems today is that the individual does not know how to behave in a critical environment. When criticizing, the person should be aware of his moral responsibility. Mankind has to observe moral principles no matter what action he takes. A person can easily make unwarranted criticisms about a subject that he has no knowledge of. It should be known that every speech that is said indiscriminately has no value. Undoubtedly, the field of activity of language is vast and unlimited. As the fields of charity are very wide, the fields of evil are also wide. Therefore, whoever releases the tip of his tongue and releases it like a free rein, the devil can take him everywhere, drag him to the edge of the abyss, and put him in a position where he tumbles down.³¹

It is our responsibility to control our language. All the statements we say without measuring or weighing harm the people in front of us. Man is a responsible being. He is responsible for every word he says and every action he takes. Our main goal during the discussion process is not to hurt the other person. We need to stay away from all kinds of discourses and actions that will offend our interlocutor. In scientific discussions, he should avoid hurting the interlocutor, raising anger, and urging the objected person to defend his words, whether true or false, in any way possible. The person whose words are objected to tries to refute the objector's words with everything he can think of. Thus, a snarl ensues between the two arguers, just like the snarl between two dogs. Each tries to bite his friend, arguing that his thoughts are more scholarly.³²

The fact that a student of science can say: Here I have reached the most accurate information shows that he has gone beyond his limits. Criticism to satisfy his ego is an immoral attitude. The main purpose is to reevaluate an idea or information waiting to be corrected. People should be able to share information, feelings, or suggestions without hesitation. Individually and socially, we can

³¹ Gazali, *İhya'ü Ulumi'd-Din*, çev. Sıtkı Güllü (İstanbul: Huzur Yayınevi, 2012), 243.

³² Gazali, *İhya'ü Ulumi'd-Din*, 266.

only lay the foundations of healthy communication with a constructive attitude in critical environments. Every action that takes place with a destructive attitude brings each other into conflict. When criticism exceeds its moral dose, it paves the way for takfirism. “Any exclusionary approach, such as takfirism and intellectualism, will cause its owner to neglect herself by always being busy investigating her mistakes and evaluating them.”³³ In a quarrel, two different groups belonging to the same religion ignore the moral boundaries by saying to each other “You are an infidel” or “You are a polytheist”. A person who crosses his moral boundaries begins to see himself as the authority to determine who is a Muslim and who is not. “There are moral and intellectual principles that must be followed when making a sound and correct criticism. These principles increase or decrease the credibility and reputation of the critic. Therefore, the moral and intellectual principles to be followed while criticizing are as follows.

1. When criticizing, approach the other person with sincere and honest actions. Do not be pessimistic, marginalizing, and hurtful.
2. When criticizing, you should not constantly target people who do not have the same ideology as you. Do not make the mistake of making takfir of those who do not have a common denominator with you.
3. Act with the stimulant and instructive principle while criticizing.
4. Set the goal of reaching the truth and ignore the desires of the soul accordingly.
5. Avoid ambiguous information while criticizing. It is not following moral principles to make use of defective, incomplete and inconsistent information in your claim that will be defended. If you have acted in such a way, that is, if you defend your thesis by putting forward false information, immediately state that you are wrong. Know that confessing is virtuous.

³³ Muhammed Şevki Aydın, *Açık Toplumda Din Eğitimi* (Ankara: Nobel Yayın Dağıtım, 2011), 150.

6. The person who will criticize should not get the feeling of getting applause or appreciation from others. This is a common phenomenon in society.

7. Your criticism should have limits. Boundless criticism paves the way for the emergence of major problems. For example, the debates over the Qur'an and the Sunnah in the geography we live in can be given as an example.

8. Do not defend your thesis with wrong historical information. Be careful not to fall into anachronism. Evaluate each case on its own terms. The prerequisite for making a correct assessment is the geography, culture and historical process in which the event took place.

9. Don't assume that the best commentary on religion is yours. Do not make such a mistake. Do not equate the interpretation of a group or segment you belong to with religion. Remember that different groups have the right to criticize. In this context, do not equate any political thought or political doctrine with religion. Keep in mind that those who try to use religion or are atheists pose a danger to you.

10. Don't forget to respect your partner. Discourses that will harm your personality should be avoided. Especially in religious discussions, it is seen that such moral principles are not acted upon.

11. Criticism should not be directed against the person. Criticism should be directed toward concepts and ideas. Such an attempt increases the efficiency of cognitive activity. Otherwise, he will always have the greed to win over his opponent. If the extent of my discussion turns into a competition, it will be far from the truth. If the idea of self gets in front of the truth in the discussion, othering, takfir and contempt come into play.

12. The person should have sufficient knowledge and equipment about the subject to be criticized. The main sources of the topic to be discussed should be referenced. You should know that second sources reach you after a second observer and reader's evaluations. In this context, you should look at the first resources,

especially the second resources that will enrich your mental world. Taking such an approach keeps you away from a reductionist identity.

13. It is necessary to know that healthy criticism is made from the inside out. The effort to make sense of the causes of the problems encountered by constantly transferring them to the outside turns into a tool that prevents seeing the weaknesses inside.

14. Do not act like a soldier of a group in your criticisms. The soldier has to defend the unit he is in. A person who constantly centers his own ideology moves away from the truth. Because he considers the truth to consist only of his own ideology. A person who clings to his own ideology tries to look for false truths even in the face of revelation. This person cannot take a step towards self-development. A person who aims at consistent and accurate criticism cannot act like a soldier. People who are strongly attached to their ideology are angry with those outside themselves. The soldier is angry because he has lost his thinking functions. An ideological mind is not a middleman. That is, he either accepts or denies everything. He cannot use his logic while making a judgment and is in sudden changes. Therefore, they envision a fictional space.

15. Do not forget that the leader of the group you are affiliated with, regardless of his knowledge of the position, cannot be faultless. Hz. Accept that there can be no other people other than the Prophet and Prophets who are infallible, free from error, and who have the will to be corrected by Allah Himself. Stay away from definitions that take people beyond being human.

16. Improve yourself constantly. Developing is not a process that you can achieve only by reading books. Keep this in mind.

17. Remember, regardless of her knowledge, experience, scientific career and social position, the knowledge produced by a person, the interpretation, and the preferred opinion cannot be equated with the Qur'an and Sunnah, which are the main sources of religion.

18. When attempting to understand and interpret religious

texts, it is necessary to know the possibilities of the language in which these texts are written. It is necessary to pay attention to the symbolic expression used in literature and the arts used. Literal readings can be misleading in this sense.

19. Do not make the mistake of generalizing while criticizing. Generally, people tend to speak in general terms. Undoubtedly, this is a necessary condition. But care must be taken when using general concepts and definitions.

20. It is necessary to use the basic concepts of Islam according to their original meanings. Undoubtedly, many basic concepts of Islam have been detached from their true meanings. For example, the concepts of destiny, will, trust, etc. are examples.³⁴

Conclusion

A critical perspective prepares people to be active rather than passive. By saving the static from life, the dynamic prepares it for life. For our lives to gain meaning, there must be questioning. When a person does not question, he becomes a slave to other thoughts. It becomes a satellite of other evil-oriented thoughts. Criticism enables people to know themselves, to understand others, and to reach the right information. Criticism helps the person to complete their deficiencies and correct their mistakes. It enables one to reach the truth. The person tries to find ways to rebuild by considering his ideas or actions, starting with himself. Self-criticism plays an important role in diagnosing a person's real problems and controlling their emotions, thoughts and behaviors. The individual's self-criticism reminds him of his responsibilities toward society. It gives the status of being a more conscious citizen in the society.

Constructive criticism is a type of criticism used by those who have moral responsibilities. In this type of criticism, it is essential to avoid behaviors that target the person or character of the person. The aim is simply to correct the misconception, taking into

³⁴ Yavuz Yılmaz, "Eleştiri Yaparken Uyulması Gereken Ahlaki ve Entelektüel ilkelere," (Erişim: 14.8.2017), <http://www.ufkumuzhaber.com>.

account moral principles. In the type of destructive criticism, it is the mindset in which moral principles are compromised and human value is disregarded. It is a type of criticism that directly targets the person's personality rather than thoughts. Most of the criticisms made with bad intentions cause turmoil among the individual or society. Adhering to moral principles is the most important turning point of the critical process for healthy communication to take place. Only when morality and criticism come together can thoughts gain meaning. On the contrary, the presentation of ideas in an environment devoid of moral values causes other problems and chaos among people. Moral behaviors help to soften the environment and finalize the most difficult problems to solve. The development of education, the spread of the student-centered education system, and the acquisition of new skills in teaching occur with the use of the critical thinking method. Thanks to this mentality, like other disciplines (Philosophy, Geography, Health, Biological and Cinema), it helps to understand concepts like an analysis machine and to obtain deeper information. Islamic thought warns about how Muslims should behave in a critical thinking environment. The messages given are extremely clear and understandable. Criticism should not distance people from each other but should bring them closer. When moral values are taken into consideration, it should be known that grudges, hatred and enmity will be doomed to disappear, and tolerance, sincerity and friendship will sprout instead.

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